

Metrics That Measure Impact

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Dr. Rebecca Ringuette, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0875-2023>

The Metrics that Measure Impact session continued last year's discussion on ways to use available metrics to assess the impact of the various hosted datasets. This year, the session began with a presentation and demonstration of the capabilities of the Science Explorer (Sci-X, <https://scixplorer.org/>) for data citation metrics presented by [Alberto Accomazzi](#). Using AI-powered citation detection, Sci-X offers data citation metrics with enhanced accuracy over existing services for publications relevant to the NASA Science Mission Directorate (SMD) science areas.

The topic of the session then turned to the problem of measuring impact. The discussion spent a considerable amount of time emphasizing the imperfect and incomplete picture that a metrics-based impact assessment gives, particularly that some important aspects of impact are not measurable by metrics. The discussion also spent some time on considering what kinds of impact were important to measure and the differences between them, such as science impact or economic impact. As long as the metrics chosen are relevant to the type of impact chosen, attendees agreed that metrics do aid in impact assessment, referencing their own related efforts presented at last year's session. The group collaborated to produce a list of metrics that could be used to measure impact, with a substantial number likely to be automatically trackable given existing capabilities on dataset landing pages, Sci-X services, and DataCite DOI metadata, and a few indicated as important but difficult to measure.

Metrics considered to be automatically trackable are:

- Direct citations (either to the data/software or the reference publication)
- Secondary citations (e.g. citations to the publication(s) the data/software is cited in)
- Number of authors/contributors
- Number of accesses
- Number of downloads
- Original data (PI) use vs. archival use (follow-up studies)
- Distance between original proposal and published studies (e.g. overlap of keywords)
- Number of times the data/page shows up in federated search
- Engagement with or of the user community
- Mentions of datasets (i.e. in the caption of the figure) but not a formal citation.

A few items were also deemed important but were indicated as difficult to measure, including:

- The number of proposals resulting from collaboration on specific datasets.
- The number of successful proposals resulting from collaboration on specific datasets.
- AI-supported analyses of the science done with data?

Based on these discussions, the **major findings and outcomes** of the session are:

- Automatically trackable impact metrics give an imperfect and incomplete portrayal of the actual impact of a dataset.
- A large sampling of metrics can be accumulated based on existing infrastructure, including Sci-X's services, information stored in DataCite's DOI metadata, and dataset landing page monitoring, although some improvements are needed.
- Other important metrics need further development or infrastructure to enable automated tracking, while still others require a human assessment.

The **next steps** are:

- Gather further input to the total list of metrics and classify new additions as currently automatically trackable, manually trackable, or non-trackable.
- Prioritize the list of manually and non-trackable metrics in need of additional support to become automatically trackable.
- Encourage collaboration across repositories to increase automated reporting for automatically trackable metrics based on existing infrastructure, including enriching the mapping between the repositories' metadata schema and the metadata stored in the DataCite DOI, collaborating with Sci-X to improve their citation tracking capabilities, and dataset monitoring statistics.